

Cobalt(II) complexes give rise to two bands around 18,000 and 20,000 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transition characteristic of octahedral Co^{II} ion in O_h symmetry^{3,6}. Electronic spectra and μ_{eff} values are in conformity with the high spin octahedral configuration of cobalt(II) complexes.

Infrared spectral data indicate that zinc complexes have an octahedral environment around the metal ion involving bidentate acetate group and the nitrogen donor ligands.

References

1. J. CATTERICK and P. THORNTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 233.
2. C. D. RAO, B. K. MOHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 631.
3. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1969, p. 870.
4. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrophotometric Identification of Organic Compounds", John Wiley, New York, 1967.
5. J. R. FERRARO, "Low Frequency Vibration of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1977.
6. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.

Complexing Behaviour of Some New Schiff Bases: High Spin Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Complexes with Tridentate and Tetradentate Schiff Base Ligands

UMA AGARWAL and GREESH SAXENA*

Chemical Research Laboratories, R. B. S. College, Agra-282 001

Manuscript received 16 June 1983, revised 9 March 1984,
accepted 30 May 1984

THE synthesis, structural investigations and reactions of metal chelates with sulphur containing Schiff's bases have received renewed attention in recent years because of their proven antitumour^{1,2} and carcinostatic activities^{3,4}. Coordination compounds of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with various Schiff bases have been studied extensively⁵⁻⁸ but little is known about the complexes of Schiff bases derived from heterocyclic glyoxalic aldehydes. Hence, an attempt has been made here to prepare and characterise nickel(II) and cobalt(II) chelates with Schiff bases derived from 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal and various amines.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade. 2-Acetyl thiophene glyoxal was prepared by the reported method⁹. The ligands were prepared by the condensation of 2-acetyl thiophene glyoxal with *p*-aminobenzoic acid, *p*-toluidine, 2-aminopyridine and *o*-phenylenediamine in absolute ethanol. These

were purified by recrystallisation from absolute ethanol. Complexes were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of ligands and metal chlorides in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 1-4 h and then concentrated to a small volume. On cooling, crystals of the complexes obtained were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air.

The analyses of carbon and hydrogen were done at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldahl's method. Metals were estimated by Vogel's method¹⁰ after decomposing the complex with a mixture of H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 . Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made by Gouy method at room temperature (288 K) using water as calibrant. Dimagnetic corrections were made by using Pascal's constants. Electronic spectra were recorded in acetone on Toshniwal visible spectrophotometer. Ir spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer model 621 spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

The complexes under investigation are listed in Table 1 along with their colour, analysis and other properties. Analytical data of these complexes reveal 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry. The molar conductance values (3.78-12.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) in acetone solution adequately confirm the non-ionic nature of the complexes¹¹. The magnetic moments of cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are in the ranges 4.65-5.05 and 2.98-3.25 B.M., respectively indicating the spin-free octahedral geometry around the metal ions¹².

The cobalt(II) complexes show two d-d bands in 15151-16260 and 18181-19610 cm^{-1} regions which may be attributed to transitions ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively. ν_1 was not observed due to instrumental limitation. ν_1 was calculated by the method (C)¹³ using the calculated values of 10 Dq and B (Table 2).

The values of transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by Konig's equations^{14,15}. The ligand field parameter B and the ligand field splitting energy (10 Dq) in case of cobalt(II) complexes were calculated¹⁶. Out of the four methods applicable in case of Cobalt(II) complexes, the best fitting method is 13C because the ratio ν_2 (obs)/ ν_1 (calcd.) is found to be around 2.14-2.15 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes, and the calculated values of 10Dq is in good agreement to that determined by ν_2 (obs) - ν_1 (calcd.). The values of β of these complexes are between 0.5-1.0 and clearly indicate the partial covalent character of the bond concerned. However, the electronic spectral data suggest octahedral geometry for all the complexes¹⁷.

The electronic spectra of nickel(II) complexes (Table 3) are consistent with their octahedral geometry showing three d-d transition bands in 10526-11364, 16129-17241 and 25000-27777 cm^{-1} regions

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	M.p. °C	Colour	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	
					C	H	N	S	M		
1.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	213	Brownish black	4.65	44.60 (44.20)	3.32 (3.40)	3.84 (3.97)	9.13 (9.07)	16.58 (16.70)	—	4.82
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ONS})_2]$	230	Dark brown	3.78	60.43 (60.36)	4.14 (4.26)	5.52 (5.42)	12.27 (12.38)	11.45 (11.99)	—	4.65
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2]$	226 ^d	Green	7.22	53.69 (53.78)	3.32 (3.26)	11.52 (11.41)	13.11 (13.04)	12.12 (12.00)	—	4.98
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$	228	Green	8.15	44.84 (44.82)	2.36 (2.49)	5.78 (5.81)	13.24 (13.28)	12.17 (12.23)	14.82 (14.73)	5.05
5.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$	245 ^d	Black	3.32	44.36 (44.20)	3.37 (3.40)	3.82 (3.97)	9.16 (9.07)	16.53 (16.64)	—	2.98
6.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ONS})_2]$	236	Black	2.56	60.32 (60.38)	4.16 (4.26)	5.54 (5.42)	12.29 (12.39)	11.44 (11.36)	—	3.25
7.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2]$	198	Greenish yellow	3.64	53.78 (53.88)	3.35 (3.26)	11.39 (11.41)	13.14 (13.04)	11.88 (11.96)	—	3.16
8.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$	181	Yellowish	1.71	44.78 (44.84)	2.41 (2.49)	5.76 (5.81)	13.12 (13.29)	12.22 (12.19)	14.83 (14.74)	3.05

d = decomposed.

TABLE 2—OBSERVED AND CALCULATED TRANSITION ENERGIES (cm^{-1}) FOR THE COBALT(II) COMPLEXES

Methods of calculation	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	B_{ss}	10Dq	$\delta\nu$	β_{ss}	$(\nu_2 - \nu_1)$	ν_2/ν_1	$\delta\nu\%$	CFSE kcal mol ⁻¹
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{NS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$											
Experimental	—	15151	18181	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
(a) fitted	fitted	18242	814	8088	+67	0.84	—	—	—	0.37	—
(b) fitted	fitted	17350	887	9250	+2199	0.91	—	—	—	12.67	—
(c) fitted	fitted	7063	809	8085	—	0.83	8088	2.15	—	—	18.48
(d) fitted	fitted	7063	15151	18181	810	8088	—	0.83	—	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{11}\text{ONS})_2]$											
Experimental	—	16129	19305	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
(a) fitted	fitted	19319	859	8608	+14	0.88	—	—	—	0.07	—
(b) fitted	fitted	18481	941	9852	+2352	0.97	—	—	—	12.73	—
(c) fitted	fitted	7521	858	8606	—	0.88	8608	2.14	—	—	19.68
(d) fitted	fitted	7521	16129	19305	858	8608	—	0.88	—	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{ON}_2\text{S})_2]$											
Experimental	—	15878	18691	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
(a) fitted	fitted	18552	813	8463	-139	0.84	—	—	—	0.75	—
(b) fitted	fitted	18244	906	9719	+2371	0.93	—	—	—	12.99	—
(c) fitted	fitted	7410	823	8467	—	0.85	8463	2.14	—	—	19.35
(d) fitted	fitted	7410	15873	18691	822	8463	—	0.85	—	—	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{S}_2)\text{Cl}_2]$											
Experimental	—	16260	19610	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
(a) fitted	fitted	19704	882	8682	+94	0.91	—	—	—	0.45	—
(b) fitted	fitted	18624	959	9931	+2363	0.99	—	—	—	12.69	—
(c) fitted	fitted	7578	875	8678	—	0.90	8682	2.15	—	—	19.83
(d) fitted	fitted	7578	16260	19610	876	8682	—	0.90	—	—	—

assignable to the transitions ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3), respectively¹⁸.

The interelectronic repulsion parameter B in case of Ni^{II} complexes has been obtained by different methods¹⁹. Transition energies calculated according to different methods show that the best fit procedure is method (C)¹³ as there is small difference in calculated transition energy and observed band energy. Electronic spectral data were used to calculate the important ligand field para-

meters 10Dq, β and λ . For d⁸ complexes with O_h symmetry, Lever²⁰ suggested that the configuration interaction between $T_{1g}(P)$ and $T_{1g}(F)$ excited states lower the ratio ν_2/ν_1 from 1.8 (theoretical) to 1.5-1.7, which is in conformity with the experimental data supporting the distortion in octahedral geometry.

The infrared frequencies of the Schiff bases and their corresponding cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are listed in Table 4. The frequencies in the free ligands at 1590-1630 (HC=N) and 1660-1720

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND VARIOUS LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF NICKEL(II) COMPLEXES

Methods of calculation	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	B_{ss}	β_{ss}	$\delta\nu$	$\frac{10Dq}{B}$	λ	ν_2/ν_1	ν_3/ν_1	f	hx	CFSE kcal mol ⁻¹	μ_{eff} Calcd. B.M.
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ NS)(H ₂ O) ₂]														
Experimental	10526	17241	26316	—	—	—	—	—	1.64	2.50	1.18	—	36.09	3.17
(a)	10Dq	fitted	29337	1000	0.96	+3021	10.53	164	—	—	—	0.33	—	—
(b)	10Dq	16541	fitted	752	0.72	-700	13.99	—	—	—	—	2.33	—	—
(c)	10Dq	16702	26846	798	0.77	+530	13.19	—	—	—	—	1.92	—	—
(d)	10Dq	16103	25180	647	0.62	-1136	16.27	—	—	—	—	3.17	—	—
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ONS) ₂]														
Experimental	10638	17241	27777	—	—	—	—	—	1.62	2.61	1.19	—	36.47	3.17
(a)	10Dq	fitted	28639	931	0.84	+862	11.43	195	—	—	—	0.92	—	—
(b)	10Dq	17050	fitted	861	0.83	-191	12.36	—	—	—	—	1.42	—	—
(c)	10Dq	17088	27936	874	0.84	+159	12.17	—	—	—	—	1.33	—	—
(d)	10Dq	16987	27527	840	0.81	-250	12.66	—	—	—	—	1.58	—	—
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ S) ₂]														
Experimental	11364	16666	26315	—	—	—	—	—	1.47	2.32	1.28	—	38.96	3.14
(a)	10Dq	fitted	25913	566	0.54	-402	20.08	88.4	—	—	—	3.83	—	—
(b)	10Dq	16928	fitted	610	0.59	+262	18.63	—	—	—	—	3.42	—	—
(c)	10Dq	16831	26156	593	0.57	-159	19.16	—	—	—	—	3.58	—	—
(d)	10Dq	17247	26895	670	0.64	+580	16.96	—	—	—	—	3.00	—	—
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂]														
Experimental	10869	16129	25000	—	—	—	—	—	1.48	2.30	1.22	—	37.27	3.16
(a)	10Dq	fitted	25071	573	0.55	+71	18.97	79	—	—	—	3.75	—	—
(b)	10Dq	16085	fitted	565	0.54	-44	19.24	—	—	—	—	3.88	—	—
(c)	10Dq	16103	25024	568	0.55	+24	19.14	—	—	—	—	3.75	—	—
(d)	10Dq	16008	24879	552	0.53	-121	19.69	—	—	—	—	3.92	—	—

TABLE 4—SELECTED INFRARED ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹) OF COBALT(II) AND NICKEL(II) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Compd.	ν_{COOH}	$\nu_{C=O}$	$\nu_{CH=N}$	$\nu_{as(COO)}$	$\nu_s(COO)$	ν_{C-S-C}	ν_{M-N}	ν_{M-O}	ν_{M-S}	ν_{M-Cl}
C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ NS	2610 m	1720 m	1590 s	1620 m	1390 m	1220 s	—	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ NS)(H ₂ O) ₂]	—	1668 s	1580 s	1500 b	1395 m	1235 s	530 b	465 w	370 vw	—
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ NS)(H ₂ O) ₂]	—	1680 s	1585 m	1540 w	1395 w	1260 s	530 b	485 w	322 w	—
C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ONS	—	1660 s	1610 m	—	—	1240 m	—	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ONS) ₂]	—	1635 m	1580 m	—	—	1262 w	530 w	435 w	360 vw	—
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₁ ONS) ₂]	—	1715 m	1630 m	—	—	1280 m	540 w	425 w	340 w	—
C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ S	—	1660 s	1610 w	—	—	1225 m	—	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ S) ₂]	—	1650 m	1590 s	—	—	1155 m	535 w	425 w	338 w	—
[Ni(C ₁₁ H ₉ ON ₂ S) ₂]	—	1640 m	1585 s	—	—	1260 s	525 b	440 w	355 w	—
C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	—	1660 m	1630 m	—	—	1265 w	—	—	—	—
[Co(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂]	—	1620 s	1570 m	—	—	1262 s	580 m	460 w	—	265 m
[Ni(C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂)Cl ₂]	—	1640 w	1565 w	—	—	1260 m	560 m	432 w	—	270 w

s=strong, m=medium, w=weak, b=broad, vw=very weak.

cm⁻¹ (C=O) shift to lower frequency in the complexes showing coordination of metal ion through these groups. Thiophene stretching frequency in the region 1220-1265 cm⁻¹ shows a shift of 15-45 cm⁻¹ indicating its involvement in chelation except for the complexes [Co(C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂S₂)Cl₂] and [Ni(C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂S₂)Cl₂]. The frequency 2610 cm⁻¹ (COOH) in the ligand C₁₂H₈O₃NS disappears in the complexes. The symmetric and asymmetric stretching band on complexation also get shifted indicating the involvement of carboxylic group in bonding²¹.

Appearance of new bands at 525-580, 425-485 and 322-370 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to (M-N), (M-O) and (M-S) stretching frequencies, respectively supporting chelation through these groups. In the

complexes [Co(C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂S₂)Cl₂] and [Ni(C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂S₂)Cl₂] the bands at 265 and 270 cm⁻¹, respectively are assigned to M-Cl stretching mode²².

References

1. E. M. HODNETT, C. H. MOORE and F. A. FRENCH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 1121.
2. A. CHIRIAC, O. DRAGOMIR, F. MOTOC and I. MOTOC, *Ser. Chim.*, 1979, 1, 3.
3. M. AKBARALI, S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 13, 101.
4. D. T. CHAUDHARY and S. S. SABNIS, *Bull. Hoffmann Inst.*, 1976, 4, 85.
5. E. VERDA, N. MATSUOKA and Y. SHIMURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1982, 55, 136.
6. R. PASTORIK and F. BRZINA, *Z. Chem.*, 1981, 21, 39.

7. B. CHISWELL, J. P. CRAWFORD and E. J. O' RILLIV, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1980, **40**, 223.
8. V. P. KURBATOV, T. V. TORGova, O. A. OSIPOV and N. A. BELONOG, *Koord. Khim.*, 1981, **7**, 207.
9. F. KIPNIS and J. ORNFELT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2734.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London 8rd ed., 1969.
11. W. J. GEARY, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1971, **7**, 81.
12. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, **6**, 197.
13. N. A. PATRI, J. R. SHAH and R. P. PATRI, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 236.
14. E. KONIG, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **10**, 2632.
15. E. KONIG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 1173, 2877.
16. H. S. VERMA, A. PAL, R. C. SAXENA and A. K. KATIYAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 84.
17. A. B. P. LEVER and D. OGDEN, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 2041.
18. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
19. E. KONIG *Struct. Bonding (Berlin)*, 1971, **9**, 175.
20. A. B. P. LEVER, *Adv. Chem.*, 1966, **62**, 435.
21. B. SINGH, V. BANERJEE, B. V. AGARWALA and A. K. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 36.
22. G. PANTICELLI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 45.

A Study in the Complex Formation of Thiodiacetic, Thiodipropionic, Dithiodiacetic, Iminodiacetic and Oxydiacetic Acids with Nickel and Copper Ions

S. N. DUBEY,* R. K. BAWEJA and D. M. PURI

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University,
Kurukshetra-132 119

*Manuscript received 3 April 1983, revised 24 January 1984,
accepted 17 June 1984*

A survey of the literature¹⁻⁴ revealed that no effort appears to have been made to determine the thermodynamic stability constants of the complexes formed by Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} ions with thiodiacetic acid (TDAA), thiodipropionic acid (TDPA), dithiodiacetic acid (DTDAA), iminodiacetic acid (IDAA) and oxydiacetic acid (ODAA). In view of the above and also the results reported⁵⁻⁷ by us on the chelation abilities of the above mentioned ligands, it was considered of interest to study Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} systems potentiometrically. The thermodynamic stability constants of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes were obtained by extrapolating the determined stability constants at various ionic strengths (0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M, 25°) to zero ionic strength. The thermodynamic functions (ΔG , ΔH and ΔS) were calculated at 0.1 M. The titration technique adopted was that of Calvin and Wilson as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁸⁻¹⁰.

Experimental

The solutions of TDAA, TDPA and DTDAA (Evan's), IDAA (Sigma), ODAA (John Backer), nickel sulphate (NiSO₄·H₂O, A.R.) and copper sulphate (CuSO₄·5H₂O, A.R.) were prepared in double distilled water. Perchloric acid (0.04 M)

solution was prepared from the stock solution by dilution with double distilled water and standardised against standard NaOH solution. Other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The stock solutions of nickel sulphate and copper sulphate were standardised gravimetrically.

A Philips (PR 9405 M) pH meter with glass and calomel electrodes assembly was used to measure the pH. The instrument was calibrated at pH 4.0 and 9.2. The experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹¹. An appropriate quantity of sodium perchlorate (2.0 M) was added to maintain the desired ionic concentrations at 0.1, 0.2 and 0.3 M.

Results and Discussion

The pH range investigated for Ni^{II}-TDAA, Ni^{II}-TDPA, Ni^{II}-DTDAA, Ni^{II}-IDAA, Ni^{II}-ODAA, Cu^{II}-TDAA, Cu^{II}-TDPA, Cu^{II}-IDAA and Cu^{II}-ODAA systems were 2.45-4.80, 3.60-4.70, 3.50-4.70, 2.80-6.80, 3.40-5.20, 2.40-5.20, 3.20-4.40, 2.40-7.40 and 2.60-3.20, respectively.

The proton-ligand stability constants of TDAA, TDPA, DTDAA, IDAA and ODAA, and the stepwise formation constants of their chelates with Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} were determined at 25±0.5, 35±0.5 and 45±0.5° using Irving-Rossotti technique and the values were further refined using the computational techniques^{12,13}, (i) curvefitting method and (ii) pointwise calculation method. The protonation constant values of TDAA, TDPA, DTDAA, IDAA and ODAA determined at different ionic concentrations and temperatures are the same as reported earlier⁶. The stepwise formation constants of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates are given in Table 1.

In Ni^{II}-TDPA, Ni^{II}-DTDAA, Ni^{II}-ODAA, Cu^{II}-TDPA and Cu^{II}-ODAA systems, the $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.1 and 0.9, thereby indicating the formation of only 1:1 complex. In Ni^{II}-TDAA, Ni^{II}-IDAA, Cu^{II}-TDAA and Cu^{II}-IDAA systems, $\bar{n}$ values varied between 0.2 and 1.9, indicating the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. Cu^{II}-DTDAA systems could not be studied as precipitation starts from the very beginning.

It is evident from Table 1 that metal-ligand formation constants increase with increase in ionic strength and decrease with increase in temperature. The thermodynamic formation constants were evaluated by extrapolating the concentration formation constants to zero ionic strength and the values are given in Table 1. The general trend in the overall thermodynamic stabilities indicates that the Cu^{II} complexes are more stable as compared to the Ni^{II} complexes.

The thermodynamic functions ΔG , ΔH and ΔS were calculated using the standard equations¹⁴ and the values are given in Table 2. Chelates of Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with the ligands are formed spontaneously as revealed by the negative ΔG values. The overall changes in ΔH and ΔS values indicate that